

Full Length Article

Reversible and irreversible structural changes in FeO/Ru(0 0 0 1) model catalyst subjected to atomic oxygen

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Iron monoxide (FeO)

Ru(0 0 0 1)

Model catalyst

Oxidation

Atomic oxygen

Structure

ABSTRACT

Islands and thin films of metal oxides grown on metal single-crystal supports constitute well-defined model systems for studying elementary steps of catalytic reactions that take place at the surface of metal-oxide catalysts. Fundamental studies carried out under idealized ultra-high vacuum (UHV) conditions have to be, however, linked to the industrial ones by overcoming the so called “pressure gap”. In the case of oxidation reactions, experiments using high (millibar) oxygen pressures or moderate pressures of highly oxidative gaseous species (such as atomic oxygen) are commonly performed to bridge (at least partially) the two catalytic worlds. We studied the structural changes that occur in ultrathin iron monoxide (FeO) islands and films grown on single-crystal Ru(0 0 0 1) substrate upon exposure to atomic oxygen. The results reveal that room-temperature exposure leads to the formation of oxygen-rich and structurally ill-defined iron oxide and ruthenium oxide species. The transformation can be, however, reverted by vacuum annealing. Exposing FeO/Ru(0 0 0 1) to atomic oxygen at 700 K leads, on the other hand, to an irreversible transformation of the iron oxide to a Fe₂O₃-like phase. The results contribute to the general understanding of the oxidation reactions over metal-oxide catalysts.

1. Introduction

Model studies in heterogeneous catalysis aim at the determination of reaction mechanisms by using simplified and well-defined sample systems and performing reactions under strictly-controlled conditions [1]. In such studies, the catalytic processes are often divided into elementary steps that are studied separately and in-depth using surface science techniques under ultra-high vacuum (UHV). One of the biggest groups of catalytic materials used industrially are those based on metal oxides, commonly employed, e.g., in oxidation reactions [2]. In model studies, such systems can be mimicked by depositing metal (/oxide) nanoparticles onto an oxide (/metal) single-crystal support. In order to avoid charging problems commonly encountered during surface science studies of oxide materials, thin oxide films grown on electrically-conducting substrates, instead of bulk oxides, are being used [3]. It is much more difficult to mimic in laboratory conditions the reaction conditions that are present in an industrial catalytic reactor, i.e. high pressures of gases, high temperatures and the presence of common contaminants (such as H₂O). In particular, the interaction of gases at high pressures with the surface of the catalyst can significantly differ from the

interaction of the same gases at much lower pressures. This is related to different chemical potential of the gas at different pressures and is commonly referred to as the “pressure gap”. In the case of oxidation reactions, such as carbon monoxide (CO) to carbon dioxide (CO₂) oxidation, it is possible to mimic the high chemical potential of molecular oxygen (O₂) by using lower pressure of a more strongly oxidizing agent, e.g. atomic oxygen (O_{at}). Such approach was found to successfully reproduce the oxidizing effect of the millibar pressures of O₂ (even though those are still much lower than the pressures used industrially) [4–6].

Iron oxide films grown on single-crystal platinum substrates [7] were shown to be suitable model systems for studying the mechanisms of various catalytic reactions (see the review articles [8,9]). Those studies led to the discovery of the superior activity of ultrathin iron monoxide (FeO) islands and films on Pt(1 1 1) in the low temperature CO oxidation reaction at millibar pressures [10], related both to the limited thickness of the oxide layer and the electronic interaction with the underlying platinum support [4]. The main role of the oxide in this reaction is to promote the dissociation of O₂ [4,11,12]. The process results in the formation of weakly bound oxygen (WBO) species [13]

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2020.146032>

Received 31 October 2019; Received in revised form 29 February 2020; Accepted 9 March 2020

Available online 13 March 2020

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which can react with the CO molecules adsorbed on the exposed areas of the substrate (through a dual-site Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism) [12] or present in the gas phase (Mars-van Krevelen mechanism) [14]. However, in the case of laterally large FeO crystallites and closed FeO films, high oxygen chemical potential is needed to transform the oxide from the initial (chemically inert) O-Fe-Pt structure to a catalytically-active O-Fe-O-Pt (FeO_{2-x}) phase which hosts WBOs [4,15]. Even though the direct relation of these findings with the processes occurring at the surfaces of real iron oxide/platinum catalysts is not known, some reports show a possible link [12,16].

The role of the single-crystal support in the catalytic activity of FeO was further verified by comparing the activity of FeO islands and films grown on Pt(1 1 1) and Au(1 1 1) [17]. Much weaker interaction of the oxide with Au(1 1 1) led to significant structural transformations in the film when subjected to reaction conditions and inhibited the formation of a stable FeO_{2-x} phase that could be reversibly oxidized and reduced (by O_2 and CO in the reactor, respectively) in the course of the reaction (as can be done for the film on Pt(1 1 1) [14] and FeO islands on both supports [18–21]). Very weak adsorption of CO on Au(1 1 1) also excluded one of the two possible reaction mechanisms [17].

We studied ultrathin FeO islands and films grown on another noble metal single-crystal substrate – Ru(0 0 1) [22] – focusing on the structural changes that occur in this system upon exposure to strongly oxidizing conditions, i.e. O_{at} at room temperature (RT) and 700 K. FeO/Ru(0 0 1) differs significantly from FeO/Pt(1 1 1) [7] and FeO/Au(1 1 1) [23]. The most stable FeO form on Ru(0 0 1) is the O-Fe-O-Fe-Ru bilayer, and not the O-Fe monolayer, as in the case of the above-mentioned supports. Ruthenium is also much more prone to oxidation [24] than Pt(1 1 1) and Au(1 1 1) and favors CO adsorption [25]. FeO/Ru(0 0 1) is, therefore, a promising candidate for the studies of the CO oxidation reaction. Our scanning tunneling microscopy (STM), low energy electron diffraction (LEED) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) results reveal that O_{at} exposure at RT leads to the formation of structurally ill-defined iron oxide and ruthenium oxide species which host a significant amount of WBOs. The structural transformation is a result of the increase in the oxidation state of iron and the oxidation of the ruthenium substrate underneath FeO. Importantly, the transformation can be reverted by vacuum annealing at 800–1000 K. Exposing FeO/Ru(0 0 1) to atomic oxygen at 700 K leads, on the other hand, to irreversible transformation of the iron oxide to a Fe_2O_3 -like phase that decomposes upon heating above 800 K in UHV.

2. Experimental details

The experiments were performed in an UHV chamber (from Omicron) with a base pressure of 5×10^{-10} mbar. The chamber was equipped with standard substrate cleaning (sputter gun, e-beam heating stage) and thin film growth (evaporator, gas line) facilities. It also hosted an atomic oxygen source (OBS 40-A; Dr. Eberl MBE-Komponenten). The Ru(0 0 1) single-crystal substrate (99.99%; MaTeck) was cleaned by repeated cycles of 1 keV Ar^+ (99.999%; Linde) ion sputtering at RT, annealing in 1×10^{-6} mbar O_2 (99.995%; Linde) at ~ 940 K (to remove residual carbon) and in UHV at 1450–1500 K. The temperature of the sample was monitored using an infrared pyrometer (Land Instruments). Ultrathin FeO islands were grown following the modified procedure of Ketteler et al. [22], i.e. by deposition of 1 monolayer (ML) of Fe (99.995%; Alfa Aesar) onto the substrate held at 500 K (to obtain uniform Fe distribution [26]), post-oxidation in 1×10^{-6} mbar O_2 at 950 K for 5 min and cooling down in oxygen for another 5 min. Closed films were obtained by repeating the procedure until an equivalent of 2 MLs of oxidized iron was present at the surface, and by performing a final flash in O_2 to 1000 K. The FeO structures (islands or films) were then exposed to O_{at} , either at RT or 700 K. The O_{at} source was operated at 1550°C under an O_2 pressure of 1×10^{-6} mbar which, according to the manufacturer, results in a nominal cracking efficiency between 10% and 20%. The samples were then

stepwise annealed in vacuum up to 1000 K to investigate their thermal stability. The cleanliness of the substrate, the FeO coverage and the topography of the samples following each preparation step, were studied using STM (CreaTec) operating in constant current mode. The images were obtained at 77 K using Pt80Ir20 tips and processed using Gwyddion computer software (gwyddion.net). The “x”, “y” and “z” dimensions were calibrated using a Au(1 1 1) test sample, with the “z” additionally calibrated for each image with respect to the height of a monoatomic step on clean Ru(0 0 1) (2.14 \AA [27]). The crystalline ordering in the samples was monitored using LEED and the chemical composition was studied using XPS (both instruments from Omicron). The XPS setup consisted of a non-monochromatized $\text{Al}_{K\alpha}$ (1486.6 eV) X-ray source and a channeltron-based hemispherical electron energy analyzer. The spectra were recorded at grazing emission using a pass energy of 20 eV. The obtained data were calibrated with respect to the position of the Ru $3d_{5/2}$ peak (280.0 eV [28]) and fitted using CasaXPS computer software (Casa Software Ltd). For the fitting of the Fe 3p line, a GL(60) lineshape (a Gaussian/Lorentzian product with a weight of 60% Lorentzian) and proper physical constraints [29] were applied. The Fe 3p peak lies in the vicinity of the Ru 4p line, therefore, the latter was included in the fitting in order to better reproduce the background and avoid fitting artefacts. The O 1s region was fitted using a GL(30) lineshape.

3. Results and discussion

Firstly, we studied the structural transformations that occur in ultrathin FeO islands (0.5 ML coverage) on Ru(0 0 1) upon exposure to O_{at} at RT for 15 min (which, taking the cracking efficiency of the atomic oxygen source into account, corresponds to a total O_{at} dose between 20 and 40 MLs). The STM images showing the islands before and after the exposure are presented in Fig. 1(a) and (b), respectively. The pristine islands are characterized by sharp edges running along the crystallographic directions of the Ru(0 0 1) support, atomic period of 3.08 \AA , a Moiré pattern with 21.6 \AA periodicity (both visible in the inset to Fig. 1(a)) – originating from the lattice mismatch between bulk FeO (1 1 1) (3.04 \AA) and Ru(0 0 1) (2.71 \AA) – and a height of approx. 5 \AA (as evidenced by the black height profile presented in Fig. 1(f) [22]). The measured height indicates the formation of bilayer (O-Fe-O-Fe) iron oxide islands, which is in agreement with the amount of deposited iron (1 ML) and the determined islands coverage (approx. 50%). Also, as pointed out by Palacio et al. [30], the bilayer is the expected FeO form for the growth carried out in O_2 pressures higher than 1×10^{-7} mbar. The exposed Ru(0 0 1) regions surrounding the FeO islands were covered by domains of chemisorbed oxygen atoms in a (2×2) or (1×2) arrangement (as observed on atomically-resolved STM images; not shown) [27]. Following the exposure to O_{at} at RT, a substantial increase of the surface roughness was observed – both on the FeO islands and the surrounding Ru areas. The species responsible for the roughness increase had a form of solid particles, which indicated further oxidation of Fe and Ru. In addition, the iron oxide islands (further denoted as FeO_x) became higher (apparent height) by $\sim 0.40 \pm 0.15 \text{ \AA}$ (see the red line in Fig. 1(f) and did no longer exhibit the characteristic atomic or Moiré structures (in fact, no ordered structure was observed; inset to Fig. 1(b)). The species covering the exposed ruthenium regions (further denoted as RuO_x) were also structurally ill-defined.

To check the thermal stability of the O_{at} -oxidized sample, we stepwise annealed it in UHV at 600, 800 and 1000 K, recording STM images after each annealing step. Following annealing at 600 K for 10 min (Fig. 1(c) and the inset to the figure), the roughness of both surface regions decreased, however, more pronouncedly on the exposed Ru(0 0 1) areas (the iron oxide islands still exhibited significant amount of structurally ill-defined protrusions). Subsequent annealing at 800 K for the same amount of time resulted in almost complete removal of protrusions – both from the iron oxide islands and the ruthenium substrate – as well as the re-appearance of the characteristic FeO Moiré

Fig. 1. STM images of FeO islands on Ru(0 0 0 1) before (a) and after (b) exposure to O_{at} at RT, as well as after additional annealing in UHV at 600 (c), 800 (d) and 1000 K (e) for 10 min. The inset in (a) shows the detailed structure of FeO, i.e. the atomic structure and the Moiré superstructure. Insets in (b–e) show zoom-ins of the respective figures. (f) presents height profiles taken over the islands in (a) (black), (b) (red) and (e) (beige) (see text for details). Image sizes: $300 \times 300 \text{ nm}^2$ (a–e), $7 \times 7 \text{ nm}^2$ (inset to (a)) and $50 \times 50 \text{ nm}^2$ (insets to (b–e)); V_{sample} : +1.0 V (all images except the insets to (a) and (d)), –70 mV (inset to (a)), +0.5 V (inset to (d)); I : 0.3 (a) and 0.1 nA (b–e, insets). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

structure (Fig. 1(d) and the inset to the figure). Also, patches of (2×2) -arranged oxygen could be again observed on the exposed ruthenium areas (see the bottom part of the inset to Fig. 1(d)). Further annealing at 1000 K did not affect the surface structure significantly, except for the disappearance of the remaining protrusions (Fig. 1(e)). A height profile taken over one of the 1000 K-annealed iron oxide islands (beige line in Fig. 1(f)) revealed that the islands became again virtually-identical in height to pristine FeO. This suggested that vacuum annealing could transform the system back to its original form, i.e. bilayer FeO(1 1 1) islands on Ru(0 0 0 1).

The O_{at} oxidation at RT and subsequent UHV annealing were also tracked by LEED. The diffraction pattern obtained for pristine FeO/Ru(0 0 0 1) sample is shown in Fig. 2(a) and consists of six intense spots in a (1×1) arrangement – originating from Ru(0 0 0 1) (the unit cell is marked with yellow rhombus), six weaker (1×1) -arranged reflexes positioned closer to the (0,0) spot (representing larger lattice constant;

white rhombus) and surrounded by satellite spots – characteristic of FeO(1 1 1) [22], as well as additional weak spots in a (2×2) arrangement (red rhombus) – that could be assigned to oxygen atoms chemisorbed on the exposed ruthenium regions and forming (2×2) - or (2×1) -arranged domains. Following the O_{at} exposure at RT, the satellite and (2×2) spots disappeared and the (1×1) spots of Ru(0 0 0 1) became more diffuse – Fig. 2(b). The disappearance of the satellite spots was in agreement with the STM results which revealed significant roughening of the surface of iron oxide islands (Fig. 1(b)). Notably, following the oxidation, the islands seemed to exhibit a slightly smaller atomic spacing (by approx. 2%, as determined from Fig. 2(b)). Similar lattice contraction was observed for FeO on Au(1 1 1) subjected to millibar pressures of molecular oxygen, where the lattice spacing decreased from 3.19 (pristine FeO) to 3.06 Å (strongly oxidized) [17]. Following annealing at 1000 K, the arrangement of spots observed for the pristine FeO sample was recovered (superposition of Ru(0 0 0 1)-

Fig. 2. LEED patterns of the sample consisting of FeO islands (0.5 ML coverage) on Ru(0 0 0 1) before (a) and after (b) O_{at} exposure at RT, as well as after additional annealing in UHV at 1000 K for 10 min (c). (d) presents the patterns obtained for clean Ru(0 0 0 1) exposed to O_2 at 950 K for 15 min (left) and O_{at} at RT for 15 min (right). Energy: 64 eV.

(1 × 1) spots, FeO(1 1 1)-(1 × 1) spots, satellite spots and O-(2 × 2) spots – Fig. 2(c)), indicating the reduction of iron oxide, the decomposition of ruthenium oxides and the formation of a layer of chemisorbed oxygen atoms on ruthenium (with the higher intensity of (2 × 2) spots indicating higher oxygen coverage).

To address the disappearance of the (2 × 2) spots and the diffuse character of the ruthenium spots following the O_{at} exposure, we performed a blank experiment in which we exposed a clean Ru(0 0 1) crystal to O₂ at 950 K (thus simulating the conditions present during the FeO growth) and to O_{at} at RT. The results, shown on the left and right side of Fig. 2(d), respectively, revealed that the former conditions promote the formation of a (2 × 2) (or (2 × 1)) oxygen arrangement, while the latter lead to (1 × 1) oxygen arrangement and blurring of the Ru(0 0 1)-(1 × 1) spots. The evolution of the pattern from (2 × 2) to (1 × 1) following highly oxidizing treatment is in agreement with the literature reports and indicates the increase of the oxygen coverage on Ru(0 0 1) [31,32]. Spots blurring, on the other hand, may be rationalized by the formation of RuO_x clusters (that can be seen on STM images shown in Fig. 1(b)).

Secondly, we exposed a pristine 0.5 ML FeO/Ru(0 0 1) sample to O_{at} at 700 K. The STM image obtained for such sample, shown in Fig. 3(a), revealed that upon O_{at} treatment the initial, relatively big, FeO islands of uniform height (like those shown in Fig. 1(a)) transformed into smaller ones exhibiting three distinguishable height levels (see Fig. 3(b) and a cyan height profile in Fig. 1(f)). The lowest one had a height of $4.8 \pm 0.1 \text{ \AA}$ – slightly lower than pristine FeO. It also exhibited a $36.0 \pm 0.2 \text{ \AA}$ superstructure with triangular symmetry (inset to Fig. 3(a)) and an atomic period of approx. 3.5 \AA (difficult to determine precisely due to high surface corrugation; Fig. 3(d)). Taking into account the applied oxidation conditions and looking at the iron

oxide phase diagram [33], it is tempting to assign the newly-formed phase to a Fe₂O₃-like structure with “biphase” surface reconstruction [34] (or at least a transition state towards one). In such a case, the observed height would roughly correspond to two Fe₂O₃ unit cells measured along the [0 0 0 1] direction. The (1 × 1) termination of Fe₂O₃ is characterized by a 5 Å atomic spacing, however, as shown in Ref. [35], the Fe atoms in Fe₂O₃ may exhibit unique structural arrangements when located at the interface with the metal substrate, which could explain the observed ~3.5 Å atomic periodicity. It also has to be noted that a strongly oxidizing treatment (exposure to mbar pressure of O₂) of FeO on Pt(1 1 1) carried out at the same temperature (700 K) did not lead to similar phase transformation [14]. This can, however, be related to the lower amount of Fe atoms per surface volume unit (preferential formation of monolayer FeO film on Pt(1 1 1), and not bilayer like in the case of Ru(0 0 1)), which makes the formation of Fe₂O₃ unit cell on Pt(1 1 1) improbable. The middle level of the islands, roughly two times higher than the first one, exhibited a partially-ordered superstructure (shown in the inset to Fig. 3(b)) with periodicity similar to the lowest one. The highest level, on the other hand, did not exhibit any ordered surface structure. Interestingly, the exposed ruthenium areas seemed to be atomically-flat, which could either indicate the formation of well-ordered ruthenium oxide or the presence of a layer of chemisorbed oxygen atoms in a (1 × 1) arrangement. The former hypothesis could be excluded, as RuO₂ crystallizes in a rutile crystal structure which would lead to the appearance of a stripe-like structure in STM [31].

In order to check, if the as-treated sample can be, similarly to the one exposed to O_{at} at RT, transformed back to the pristine state (FeO/Ru(0 0 1)) simply by thermal treatment, we subjected it to UHV annealing at 800 and 1000 K for 10 min. As evident from Fig. 3(b),

Fig. 3. STM images of FeO islands on Ru(0 0 1) subjected to O_{at} at 700 K (a) and subsequently annealed in UHV at 800 (b) and 1000 K (c) for 10 min. Cyan and pink lines in (a) and (b), respectively, correspond to the height profiles shown in Fig. 1(f). The insets in (a) and (b) show zoom-ins of the structures marked with white and orange rectangles, respectively. (d) presents an atomic-resolution image of the superstructure shown in the inset to (a), while the inset in (d) shows a FFT of the image. (e) presents a LEED pattern of a sample prepared in the same way as the one shown in (a), while (f) presents a pattern obtained for a clean Ru(0 0 1) crystal subjected to identical O_{at} treatment at 700 K. STM image sizes: $300 \times 300 \text{ nm}^2$ (a–c) and $50 \times 50 \text{ nm}^2$ (insets to (a) and (b)); $V_{\text{sample}}: +1.0 \text{ V}$ (a–c, insets), $+80 \text{ mV}$ (d); $I_t: 0.1 \text{ nA}$ (a–c, insets), 0.95 nA (d). LEED: 64 eV .

annealing at 800 K resulted in partial disordering of the first- and third-level structures, but improved the ordering of the second-level superstructure (which, despite that, was still very irregular – see the black arrows in Fig. 1(f)). Annealing at 1000 K, on the other hand, led to complete disordering of the iron oxide islands (Fig. 3(c)).

The LEED pattern corresponding to the preparation shown in Fig. 3(a) is presented in Fig. 3(e). Only diffuse (1×1) spots could be observed, which confirmed significant disordering of the FeO islands (disappearance of the FeO(1 1 1)- (1×1) spots and the satellite spots) and (1×1) ordering of oxygen on Ru(0 0 1) (lack of (2×2) spots or additional reflexes that could be assigned to RuO₂ [32,36]). The absence of additional spots originating from the triangular superstructure observed in STM on the lowest level could be explained by its relatively low coverage, as well as the limited sensitivity of our conventional LEED instrument. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the STM image of the superstructure (shown in the inset to Fig. 3(d)) revealed that the expected pattern should be similar to that of pristine FeO and consist of (1×1) -arranged iron oxide spots and satellite spots surrounding them. The (1×1) oxygen ordering on the exposed Ru(0 0 1) regions was further confirmed by exposing a clean Ru(0 0 1) crystal to O_{at} at 700 K (blank experiment), which also resulted in a diffuse (1×1) LEED pattern (Fig. 3(f)).

To get more insight into the structural evolution of the samples, we performed XPS measurements after each preparation step. We first analyze the spectra obtained for the sample exposed to O_{at} at RT. Fig. 4 shows detailed Fe 2p (a), Fe 3p (b), O 1s (c) and Ru 3d (d) XPS spectra recorded for pristine FeO islands on Ru(0 0 1) (black curve), FeO/Ru(0 0 1) exposed to O_{at} at RT (red) and subsequently annealed in UHV at 600, 800 and 1000 K for 10 min (green, blue and purple curves, respectively). The Fe 2p spectra of iron oxides are quite complex, as the spin-orbit doublet is accompanied by multiplet splitting effects and intense shake-up satellites [37]. Therefore, an accurate deconvolution of the components is not trivial. To allow a simpler analysis, the expected [29,38] positions of the Fe 2p_{3/2} and Fe 2p_{1/2} peaks of Fe⁰ (metallic), Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ iron were marked on the recorded spectra (Fig. 4(a)) with grey, red and blue vertical lines, respectively. It can be observed that for all the spectra the positions of the two maxima lie in between the binding energy expected for the Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺ states, slightly more shifted towards the former. However, the Fe 2p_{3/2} satellites expected at around 718 eV and 715 eV for Fe³⁺ and Fe²⁺,

respectively, are not clearly visible on the spectrum obtained for pristine FeO (black curve). Following the O_{at} exposure (red curve), the 718 eV satellite appeared and the main peaks at 710 and 725 eV got narrower from the low binding energy side. Fe 2p_{1/2} peak also shifted towards the 724.4 eV value expected for the Fe³⁺ iron. This suggested that the initial FeO film consists of a mixture of Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions and that the ratio between these components moves in favor of the Fe³⁺ upon O_{at} exposure. Such behavior was confirmed by the inspection of the corresponding Fe 3p spectra (Fig. 4(b)), for which a more quantitative analysis was possible thanks to the lack of multiplet and satellite features [29,37,39]. For pristine FeO, the Fe 3p region showed a single feature centered at around 55 eV, which was again an intermediate energy between the ones expected for Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ iron (53.7 and 55.6 eV, respectively [29]). This unusual peak position and its relatively high full width at half maximum (FWHM) suggested that it is a sum of at least two unresolved contributions. We, therefore, fitted the lines with two components centered at positions characteristic of Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ (for the fittings, see Fig. 6(a) and (b)). The results of the analysis are summarized in the top part of Fig. 5. For the pristine FeO film, the Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ contributions coexist with an approximate ratio of 1:1. Upon the O_{at} exposure at RT, the ratio shifts in favor of the Fe³⁺ component (84% Fe³⁺ and 16% Fe²⁺) – coherently with the narrowing peak width and the corresponding change observed in the Fe 2p spectra (Fig. 4(a)).

We then analyzed the O 1s spectra (Fig. 4(c)). For the pristine FeO sample, a broad and asymmetric peak centered at around 530 eV was observed. The shape and width of the peak indicated again that it is a superposition of different components. Fig. 6(c) and (d) show the spectra recorded for FeO/Ru(0 0 1) before (6(c)) and after (6(d)) O_{at} exposure. The total intensity could be fitted with five components centered at around 528.9, 529.9, 530.9, 532.1 and 533.4 eV, respectively, the first of which got relevant only after atomic oxygen treatment. Comparing the positions of the components with the O1s XPS data published by other groups for FeO/Ru(0 0 1) [30,40] and FeO/Pt(1 1 1) [5,19,41,42], we assigned the peak at 529.9 eV (O(1)) to originate from oxygen atoms in the FeO lattice (with iron either in Fe²⁺ or Fe³⁺ state), the peak at 530.9 eV (O(2)) to oxygen atoms in the hydroxyl groups at the borders of FeO islands (where coordinatively-unsaturated ferrous sites, promoting H₂O dissociation, are present [43]), and the peaks at 532.1 (O(3)) and 533.4 eV (O(4)) to CO and H₂O

Fig. 4. XPS Fe 2p (a), Fe 3p (b), O 1s (c) and Ru 3d (d) core level spectra recorded for pristine FeO islands on Ru(0 0 1) (black curve), the sample exposed to O_{at} at RT (red) and subsequently annealed in UHV at 600 (green), 800 (blue) and 1000 K (purple) for 10 min. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. The relative amount of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺ iron ions, as obtained from the numerical fits of the Fe 3p XPS data recorded at different stages of sample preparation.

Fig. 6. Deconvoluted Fe 3p (a, b) and O 1s (c, d) XPS spectra obtained for pristine FeO islands on Ru(0 0 0 1) before (a, c) and after (b, d) O_{at} exposure at RT. The two different components used for the Fe 3p region fitting correspond to Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺, while the five different components used to fit the O 1s region correspond to O-Fe and O-Ru (O(1)), -OH groups and satellite (O(2)), CO (O(3)), H₂O (O(4)) and WBOs (O(5)).

Table 1

The Relative amount of different oxygen species, normalized to the total intensity of oxygen, obtained from the numerical fits of the O 1s XPS spectra recorded at different stages of sample preparation.

	O(1) 529.9 eV O-Fe and O-Ru	O(2) 530.9 eV -OH and satellite	O(3) 532.1 eV CO	O(4) 533.4 eV H ₂ O	O(5) 528.9 eV WBOs
0.5 ML FeO/Ru(0 0 0 1)	69%	19%	8%	3%	1%
O _{at} at RT	55%	21%	10%	4%	10%
Annealing at 600 K	70%	18%	8%	2%	1%
Annealing at 800 K	69%	21%	8%	2%	0%
Annealing at 1000 K	69%	21%	8%	2%	0%
0.5 ML FeO/Ru(0 0 0 1)	68%	20%	8%	3%	1%
O _{at} at 700 K	67%	16%	6%	3%	8%
Annealing at 800 K	69%	18%	6%	3%	4%
Annealing at 1000 K	70%	16%	9%	4%	1%

contamination, respectively. Some contribution in these peaks is expected also from oxygen-containing species on the exposed Ru(0 0 0 1) regions, which appear at similar binding energy values (the chemisorbed oxygen atoms forming (2 × 2) or (2 × 1) domains should contribute to the O(1) component [44], while the -OH groups on Ru(0 0 0 1) to O(2) [28]). To double-check the proper assignment of oxygen components, we also performed XPS measurements on a clean Ru(0 0 0 1) crystal exposed to O₂ and O_{at} (spectra not shown; see the LEED patterns in Fig. 2(d) and the corresponding description of these blank experiments). A semi-quantitative analysis of the O 1s and Ru 3d peaks confirmed an O-atom coverage of 0.56 ML and 0.66 ML upon molecular and atomic oxygen exposure, respectively. The 528.9 eV component (O(5)) which, as already mentioned, was rather symbolic for pristine the FeO sample but got evident after O_{at} exposure, occurs at the binding energy value suitable for WBOs. These species were shown to be present in RuO_x [45] and FeO_x structures [19,42] formed on different supports following Ru or FeO exposure to strongly oxidizing conditions and are particularly important from the point of view of heterogeneous catalysis [19,42,46].

The top part of Table 1 summarizes the relative amount of the five oxygen species at the different stages of sample preparation. Upon O_{at} exposure, the fraction of the O(1) oxygen reduced, while the O(5) component, related to WBOs, grew accordingly. This behavior, together with the change in the Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ ratio and the observed overall increase of the total amount of oxygen with respect to iron, indicated the formation of a new, more oxidized, iron oxide phase. Determination of the exact structure of this phase was, however, not possible based on the obtained results. The high surface roughness (determined from STM images), lack of highly-ordered crystalline structure (LEED pattern) and complex chemical structure (XPS spectra) allow only a rough estimation of the stoichiometry which, based on many assumptions, can be described as FeO_x (1 < x < 2). This stoichiometry could either indicate that both FeO layers got slightly enriched with oxygen or that the top layer was strongly enriched, while the bottom stayed generally intact. It also has to be mentioned that the level of contamination (O(2), O(3) and O(4) components) slightly increased after the RT O_{at} treatment, which indicated high reactivity of both FeO_x and RuO_x species. Notably, the contribution of the component assigned to -OH groups (O(2)) was relatively high (~20%) and constant for all the preparations (pristine FeO, the sample exposed to O_{at}, annealed at 1000 K, etc.). Even though the -OH groups are known to stabilize different terminations of iron oxides (such as FeO_x (1 < x < 2) [5] and Fe₂O₃ [34]), the fact that the component was insensitive to various oxidative and reducing treatments made it difficult to believe that it only comes from the surface hydroxyl groups (or anything else at the surface). A virtually-identical component, i.e. centered at 530.9 eV and insensitive to the preparation conditions, was described in Ref. [28] for the ruthenium oxide RuO₂. Based on another work on IrO₂ [47], the Author interpreted this component as originating from many-body screening effect of the conduction electrons, and labelled it as a “satellite”. The peak observed for our samples could be related to the presence of similar effect, therefore, we

assigned it to -OH groups and satellite (as at least a partial contribution from hydroxyl groups could not be excluded as well).

Analysis of the Ru 3d doublet (Fig. 4(d)) showed a broadening towards higher binding energy values upon sample exposure to O_{at} at RT. This was due to the appearance of a new component (fit not shown), shifted with respect to the main peak by approx. 1 eV, which accounted for 11% of the total Ru 3d intensity. This component can be attributed to the nucleation of RuO_x clusters observed in STM (actually, the position is similar to that of RuO₂ [45]) or the presence of highly oxygen-coordinated ruthenium atoms [44]. We also tried to determine, if the formation of RuO_x clusters also takes place underneath FeO islands. This could explain similar roughening of both surface regions instead of the formation of a well-ordered oxygen-rich FeO_x phase (like it was in the case of FeO/Pt(1 1 1) [5,19,41,42]). For this purpose, we prepared a full FeO wetting layer on Ru(0 0 0 1) (1 ML coverage) and exposed it to O_{at} at RT. The exposure led to similar Ru 3d XPS line broadening (not shown) which indicated that O_{at} can penetrate through the iron oxide lattice (or from the step edges) and oxidize the ruthenium underneath. Therefore, we speculate that the high roughness of FeO_x islands is not only related to the structure of iron oxide, but also, indirectly, reflects the structure of the highly-oxidized and disordered substrate.

Following annealing at 600 K, the situation started to revert, i.e. the spectra (green traces in Fig. 4) looked more like those obtained for pristine FeO/Ru(0 0 0 1) (black). The additional component in the Ru 3d doublet disappeared completely, while the Fe 2p doublet slightly broadened (although, the Fe³⁺ satellite around 718 eV could still be resolved). The analysis of the Fe 3p photoemission line revealed almost equal amount of Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ (roughly 45% Fe²⁺ to 55% Fe³⁺), which indicated that the oxide had partially converted back to the FeO phase. Inspection of the O 1s spectrum confirmed this deduction and showed that the contaminant species desorbed during the annealing (600 K is for sure sufficient to desorb CO [48,49] and H₂O [50] from Ru(0 0 0 1)). The fact that the O(5) component did not fully disappear at that temperature, while the Ru 3d peak was fully restored, suggested that it was explicitly related to the overoxidized iron species which host the WBOs. After additional annealing at 800 K, the iron and oxygen XPS spectra became virtually-identical to those obtained for pristine FeO/Ru(0 0 0 1) sample – both with respect to the shape of the Fe 2p line (blue trace in Fig. 4(a)) and the relative amount of different oxygen species (Table 1). When it comes to the Ru 3d signal, no further changes were observed (please compare green and blue lines in Fig. 4(d)). Importantly, the desorption temperature of WBOs from FeO_{2-x} islands on Ru(0 0 0 1) seems to be comparable to that on Pt(1 1 1) (573 K) [19] and Au(1 1 1) (635 K) [17], which may have implications on the catalytic activity of the studied system. After further annealing to 1000 K (purple lines), no significant changes were observed in the recorded XPS spectra – in line with the STM results which revealed almost no topographical change.

For the FeO/Ru(0 0 0 1) sample exposed to O_{at} at 700 K, a slightly different picture was observed (the XPS data are summarized in Fig. 7(a-d) and in the bottom parts of Fig. 5 and Table 1). Following the

Fig. 7. XPS Fe 2p (a), Fe 3p (b), O 1s (c) and Ru 3d (d) core level spectra recorded for pristine FeO islands on Ru(0 0 0 1) (black curve), the sample exposed to O_{at} at 700 K (red) and subsequently annealed in UHV at 800 K (blue) and 1000 K (purple) for 10 min. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

exposure, a similar transformation from the mixed-oxidation state (Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} ratio of approx. 1:1) to a predominantly Fe^{3+} -containing (80%) phase was observed. The stoichiometry of the iron oxide, due to only partial ordering of the second layer and strong disordering of the third layer observed with STM (Fig. 3(a)), was unfortunately not possible to estimate. The most relevant difference between the two experiments appeared upon annealing at 800 K, where the reduction of the 700 K sample (resulting in 63% of iron in the Fe^{3+} state and 37% in the Fe^{2+} state) was significantly less pronounced than in the case of the RT-oxidized one (Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} ratio of roughly 1:1). Annealing at 1000 K resulted in an even more pronounced reduction, however, it also led to the appearance of metallic Fe (see Fig. 5). What is more, the intensity of the iron signal decreased significantly, indicating partial sublimation of iron and/or dissolution inside the ruthenium substrate. This behavior further suggested that the FeO islands, following the O_{at} exposure at 700 K, transformed to Fe_2O_3 -like structures which are less thermally stable than FeO. In fact, the iron oxide phase diagram [33] shows that under strongly reducing conditions (such as annealing in UHV at 1000 K), Fe_2O_3 can reduce to metallic iron. Even though there are no reports on the thermal stability of Fe_2O_3 films on Ru(0 0 0 1), thin Fe_2O_3 films on another single-crystal substrate – Pt(1 1 1) – were shown to decompose above 900 K, with metallic Fe diffusing into Pt [51]. Such assignment would also be in agreement with the STM results, which showed structural disordering of the sample following high-temperature annealing (Fig. 3(b) and (c)). Therefore, it may be concluded that the 700 K-transformation is irreversible.

4. Conclusions

We studied the structural transformations that take place in a model catalytic system consisting of bilayer FeO islands on Ru(0 0 0 1) upon exposure to O_{at} at RT and 700 K. The results reveal that RT-treatment leads to the formation of oxygen-rich and structurally ill-defined iron oxide and ruthenium oxide species (FeO_x and RuO_x , respectively), hosting a significant amount of catalytically-relevant WBOs. This transformation can be, however, reverted by vacuum annealing at 800–1000 K. Exposing FeO/Ru(0 0 0 1) to O_{at} at 700 K results, on the other hand, in an irreversible transformation of the iron oxide to a Fe_2O_3 -like phase, which is relatively thermally stable up to 800 K but decomposes into metallic iron when annealed at 1000 K. The results provide hints on the structural transformations that may occur in iron oxide-ruthenium catalysts under strongly oxidizing conditions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ying Wang: Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization. **Giovanni Carraro:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization. **Hubert Dawczak-Dębicki:** Investigation, Data curation. **Karol Synoradzki:** Investigation, Data curation. **Letizia Savio:** Formal analysis, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Mikołaj Lewandowski:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was financially supported by the Foundation for Polish Science (First TEAM programme, 2017-2020, grant No. First TEAM/2016-2/14 (POIR.04.04.00-00-28CE/16-00) “Multifunctional ultrathin Fe(x)O(y), Fe(x)S(y) and Fe(x)N(y) films with unique electronic, catalytic and magnetic properties” co-financed by the European Union under the European Regional Development Fund) and, in part, by the Polish Academy of Sciences/the National Research Council of Italy (PAN-CNR bilateral project “Catalytic conversion of N_2O over ultrathin iron oxide films”, 2017-2019) [52].

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